

A Qualitative Study Related Influence of Personality Contribution of Executives to Their Jobs on Job Satisfaction

Onur KAZANCI¹

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Abstract

People currently spend much of their most productive time at work place. Due to recent remote work and similar processes made possible by sophisticated developments in information technologies, it would not be wrong to suggest that employees have been in interaction with their job for 24/7. Therefore feelings of employees about their job consist areas of research, one of which is job satisfaction. Although there is a variety of approaches to relationships between job satisfaction and work performance, what is generally accepted is that job satisfaction influences both individual and organizational work performances/ satisfaction. Likewise, numerous factors with impacts on job satisfaction exist. The current study examined influences of Personality Contribution to Job of top managers and executives. The consequences of the research on face to face interview with thirty executives indicated that job satisfaction tended to create different impacts on managers who have status and managerial experiences in organizations of different industries.

Key words: job satisfaction, personality contribution to job, motivation, job performance

JEL Code: J28, M54, M12

1. Introduction

People today spend significant part of their life at work place or dealing with their jobs even in countries where people have high income levels (Brauer et al., 2023). Modern living, standards it has brought about and imposition that global culture is supposed to comply with them has caused the work to become not a means but the target instead for people in which case the concept called ‘business life’ but cited to be different from integrity of life is actually becoming the life of an individual itself.

The factors to motivate modern humans who spend much of their most productive time at work place have been influenced by the intrinsic and extrinsic

¹ Assist. Prof., PhD, Izmir Katip Çelebi University, Turkey, onur.kazanci@ikcu.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5187-2699>

elements related to work. Increase in motivation of individuals for the jobs is an element to augment their personal work performance and thus productivity of the business. Therefore, it is of great importance for businesses to increase motivation of employees.

Current research indicates that increase in performance workers is associated with supportive variables such as motivation, job satisfaction, employee commitment and leadership (Susanto et al., 2023).

Job satisfaction is a factor to have individually and organizationally impacts on work performances, based on which it is possible to say that job satisfaction can directly influence business productivity. Moreover, job satisfaction can also create influences on life satisfaction and physical wellbeing of individuals. Studies on job satisfaction is therefore one of the issues on which organizational behavioral works have long been focusing.

2. Job Satisfaction and Its Relationships with Work Performance

The question why people are supposed to work is not so simple as to reply based on such an economic thinking as the money earning just for living necessities. Individuals work for spending money and energy, involving in output of goods and services, establishing social interaction and social status as well as gaining financial income (Vroom, 1964, p. 43). In addition, people are also employed or engaged in a job to be recognized as an individual and meet many other demands for autonomy and security (Super, 1957, p. 3-14). The concept of work can be defined as an abstraction of the total of activities performed in social and physical terms by an individual to gain payment of wage or salary rather being a very existence itself (Locke, 1969).

Job satisfaction is an issue of great interest in scholar and business circles and yet concerning this concept and its related factors, there has been achieved any common definition on which everyone agrees (Aziri, 2011). O'connor et al. (1978) and Wanous et al. (1977) on their meta-analytical studies reported that job satisfaction has been influenced by a range of different variables and previously employed parameters are not sufficient for their measurements. Job satisfaction is negatively or positively influenced by organizational and psychological factors with variables to have impact on job satisfaction of every individual and their influences on them being different from each other.

Seashore & Taber (1975) state that job satisfaction influenced by different job-related and job-unrelated factors have impacts on organizational, individual and social satisfaction and dissatisfaction as well (see. Figure 1).

Figure 1 Principal Classes of Variables Correlated with Job Satisfaction

Source: (Seashore & Taber, 1975)

One of the issues to make job satisfaction important is its influences on individual and organizational work performance. However, the studies made concerned with relationship between job satisfaction and individual work performance in the literature exhibit consequences which are quite different from each other.

Claiming that impact of job satisfaction on work performance is inconsistent and misleading, Iaffaldano & Muchinsky (1985) on their comprehensive meta analytic study reported that a logical and conceivable correlation is consumed to exist between job satisfaction and work performance but the relationship between employees' job satisfaction and work performance is rather poor. However it does not mean that job satisfaction fails to influence work performance. Only these studies emphasize weak evidence that job satisfaction has a direct influence on work performance.

Locke (1970) however reported the reasons why there is no consistent relationship found between job satisfaction and work performance as follows:

- *Failure to determine individual differences between job related or job unrelated values*
- *Inability to measure differences in rewards acquired from performance*
- *Failure to measure attitudes to production itself*
- *Negligence to consider factors such as values, beliefs and case – commenting of an individual*

Organ (1988) emphasized insufficiency of the concepts to define work performance as the reason for the inexistence of strong relation between job satisfaction and individual performance. Attribution of effect of job satisfaction on work performance to only the economic parameters such as yielding and profitability means to exclude issues of human psychological welfare and social sustainability which are great source of the business.

Katzell et al. (1992) reported that job satisfaction and work performance can be in association with each other together with intrinsic and extrinsic rewards under the presence of fair management conditions. Even if job satisfaction is suspiciously seen to be an economic variable since it has been assessed as a subjective concept, it can provide usable knowledge thanks to its influences on behaviors and psychological weight (Freeman, 1977). On the other hand, job satisfaction more significantly influences work performance in complicated tasks as compared to less complex processes by means of moderators (Judge et al., 2001). Complication of performed jobs acts as a moderator between self assessment and job satisfaction (Judge et al, 2000). The psychological welfare caused by job satisfaction is one of the variables to influence work performance positively (Wright & Cropanzano, 2000). Autonomy and freedom in working methods becomes a factor to improve job internal welfare individuals and create intrinsic satisfaction in them (Cooper et al., 1998). Moreover, those satisfied with their jobs tend to have less absenteeism and more work and organizational commitments with additional feeling of satisfaction in their private life (Lund, 2003). It is necessary for businesses to improve job satisfaction in terms of higher organizational commitment in employees (Eslami & Gharakhani, 2012). Job satisfaction can increase the effect of organizational commitment on individual work performance by acting as a mediator function (Loan, 2020). Due to the influence of “*organizational citizenship behavior*” generally ignored in performance assessments on organizational commitment, it is another moderator variable to cause job satisfaction to influence work performance (Organ & Ryan, 1995). The effect of organizational commitment on job satisfaction by means of compliance, affiliation and internalization processes (O’Reilly & Chatman, 1986). High organizational commitment increases the possibility that individuals exhibit high performance as they have high performance expectations (Meyer et al., 1993). When employees feel the perception that they would have rewards from their efforts as long as they have increased job satisfaction tends to improve in them (Christen et al., 2006). The higher the increase in the values attributed to job, the more job satisfaction improves (Blood, 1969). Thus on condition that employees believe they could gain intrinsic and extrinsic rewards for work performance, their further working can be assessed to become the factor to improve job satisfaction.

Even if *organizational citizenship behavior* is not seen as an essential and not recognized by reward systems, it is the factor to add contribution to organizational effectiveness (Organ & Moorman, 1993). Assessment of organizations as existence with their own intentions interests and welfare independent of people involved in them obviously leads to a restricted and insufficient view. Organizations is a social unit where people get together under a social contract and establish a social interaction with each other (Keeley, 1988, p. 243). Attitudes of individuals in an

organization appears as a factor which influences their job satisfaction and thus work performance (Saari & Judge, 2004).

Since the activities which enable us to use individual mind, initiatives and skills are closely related to ego aka personality, they normally create further job satisfaction (Vroom, 1962). Even when individuals have to work on active and interesting jobs over long hours, they feel highly motivated and happy anyway (Beckers et al., 2004). Such kinds of jobs provide individuals with opportunity for self expression and exhibition of skills (Super, 1957, p.9-10). Individuals are observed to further increase job satisfaction by means of intrinsic and extrinsic but mostly intrinsic rewards as their performance has increased at job they are doing (Lawler & Porter, 1967). Even though out work factors influence job satisfaction of the individual, the main element is internal factors related to the job itself (Tietjen & Myers, 1998).

Judge ve Watanabe (1993) reported that job and life satisfactions are in mutually positive relationships and the effect of life satisfaction on job satisfaction is stronger than impact of job satisfaction on life satisfaction. Rode (2004) claimed that when out work satisfaction factors (family, health etc), job satisfaction has a weak direct impact on life satisfaction but self-evaluation functions as a predictor variable to influence both job and life satisfactions. Therefore, the intrinsic satisfaction of an individual can be cited to be the factor to further improve job satisfaction as compared to extrinsic elements. Similarly, Scarpello & Campbell (1983) found evidence that development and discovery of experiences of an individual at work he is doing could improve job satisfaction and thus life satisfaction.

Job satisfaction is also determined by how individuals define their jobs (Loher et al., 1985). Whether requirements are satisfied plays a role as a variable to have impacts on job satisfaction (Schaffer, 1953). Strong organizational communication which can be internalized and assumed by employees significantly increases job satisfaction (Pincus, 1986). Work-related quality, principles and standards have independent and remarkable influences on job satisfaction (Kalleberg, 1977). Without any control variables, there is a U-shape relationship between general job satisfaction and age and job satisfaction tends to decline down to 31-36 year of age (Clark et al., 1996).

There is a negative correlation between job satisfaction, leaving job, absenteeism and work accidents (Vroom, 1964, p. 186; Hellman, 1997). Personality characteristics influence that job satisfaction increases or decreases steadily (Dormann & Zapf, 2001). Current studies indicate that conformity of personality to work and work environment is a very aspect to improve job satisfaction (Ariani & Karyati, 2023). The fact that organizational climate is supportive, congenial, rewarding and democratic helps create presence of job satisfaction (Pritchard & Karasick, 1973). Conformity of the business to work and its attempt to protect and maintain the procedure by means of organizational culture is another factor to improve job satisfaction (Vitell & Davis, 1990).

A direct correlation between job satisfaction and unionization has been seen to exist as well, which is often caused by extended job tenure and has emerged since unionized employees have lost part of gains and wage or salary advantages do not increase satisfactorily just related to their long term union membership (Boris, 1979). Moreover, job satisfaction can be seen to decrease when significant differences appear between desired and perceived job attributes for those under 25 year age in particular (O'Brien & Dowling, 1981).

Quality of workplace climate with impacts on exhibition of skills and accomplishment of potentialities by employees as the factor to influence job satisfaction (Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015). Businesses where organizational structure is rather bureaucratic, autonomy can not be achieved and employees fail to find their expected freedom exhibit increased burnout and thus decreased job satisfaction (Arches, 1991). Even though manageable stress appears to be positively reflected in performances of employees in an organization, unmanageable individual and organizational stress can cause them to show behaviors of wasting their time or even sabotaging the processes (Sullivan & Bhagat, 1992). Leading to burnout, reduced self esteem, anxiety and depression in particular, poor job satisfaction can damage mental and therefore physical health and welfare (Faragher et al., 2005). Job stress related to the factors including overload, high expectations and low control can be suggested to be evidently associated with cardiovascular disorders (Ironson, 1992).

Trust eases adjustment to work in individuals and hence improve job satisfaction as well (Cain Smith, 1992). On the basis that rapid adaptation to change is a factor to increase individual performance, trust can be suggested to create a moderator effect between job satisfaction and work performance. Person-Environment Fit (PEF) which describes matching degree of individuals and the medium where they are creates job satisfaction and individual motivations in employees (Dawis, 1992).

In the light of this data, it would not be unreasonable to suggest that there is two-way positive correlation between job satisfaction and work performance, both of which influence each other directly but sometimes through intrinsic and extrinsic factors as well. It is therefore rational to say that job satisfaction is an important factor to influence individual and organizational work performances work performance. There are of course different approaches to the effect of job satisfaction on individual productivity. However, the organizational perspective in particular requires us to reasonably see that businesses whose employees are satisfied with what they are doing prove more effective and productive.

Though job satisfaction can have direct influences on individual work performance, it is clearly seen to have higher impacts on individual work performance based on different variables. Increased job satisfaction can have indirect contributions to individual work performance through higher psychological welfare, improved physical health increased work attendance, organizational commitment, demand for assuming more responsibility and its related behavior and increased motivation. In addition, individuals with higher job satisfaction are happy

and can naturally carry their happiness home where they live other than work environment. It is not wrong to say that this situation would have positive social effects as well.

3. Personality Contribution to Job (PCJ) as a Factor to Improve Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction is influenced by a variety of different factors. Elements such as organizational culture and climate, conformity to business ethics, physical working conditions and personal values can influence individual's job satisfaction. One of the most important elements to influence job satisfaction can be seen to be the conformity between personal and business characteristics and degree of importance which the employee attributes to the job that he is doing. The age of mechanization saved people from physical working necessity leaving it to machines but preventing them using his physical and psychological abilities as the main power source and finally turning him again into a machine and even a machine-like worker whose impact on what he has created can be ignored in essence of homogeneity and monotony (Herzberg et al., 1993, p. 123). Owing to increase in development and expansion of mass production and automation, this phenomenon has been gradually causing a low level worker in manufacturing sector to be cut off or alienated from what he has created aka labor- work. This situation further affects managers as well considering that managers have been climbing up organizational hierarchy and then being fully isolated from technical aspects of the output. Currently, applications of sophisticated Artificial Intelligence following mechanization and automation allow the laborer to be entirely cut off what he produces as a value even in service industry.

With the impact of technological developments, individuals are increasingly unable to add anything of themselves to their work. It can be said that automated production systems act as an emotional biosafety cabinet between employees and the goods or services they produce. Although workers may come into physical or psychological contact with the products they produce, automation decouples the individual from the product he or she produces. Automated control systems are considered the gold standard, especially in the production of tangible products, because they provide consistent and predictable outputs. However, existing automation systems are subject to human limitations as they are designed by humans to work with humans (Haight & Kecojevic, 2005). Individuals have gradually been failing to add any contribution of their own to the "work" they have produced, which prevents what has been produced from being identified with the worker causing businesses to see him just as a source to manufacture what is already designed in output plot. When individuals can not contribute anything of their own to what has been produced or their contributions is known and recognized the fall or loss of their satisfaction with the job which is supposed to be gained by them is inevitably the expected case. It is likely and inevitable that work performance of the workers whose job satisfaction decreases in possible combination of other variables could fall down as well.

The present study will examine identification of individuals with their job under the definition “Personality Contribution to Job (PCJ)” and explore the effects of PCJ on job satisfaction. The concept of PCJ is not an established concept in the literature. For this reason, it would not be correct to generalize that PCJ is a factor that directly affects job satisfaction. The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of PCJ on participants' job satisfaction experiences and to provide data that can be transferred to future studies.

Generally accepted management principles and methods intertwined with the current capitalist economy by management gurus cause managers, especially senior and top managers responsible for organizational strategies, to experience a conflict between their work and their selves. The pressure of profitability and efficiency of the global economy leads to the necessity for managers to adopt and apply similar principles like a machine, regardless of the characteristics of the work, product, business, sector, country of operation. In this case, the manager, regardless of his/her job and position in the organizational hierarchy, feels alienation from his/her work.

The concept of alienation from work is based on the writings of Marx, who argued that creative activity is an important need of human nature and that this need is satisfied by the "work" of the individual (Mottaz, 1981). According to Marx, in his productive, social and sensory life, man realizes his individuality and himself as a "person" through his spontaneous and unhindered productivity (Cotgrove, 1972). Man, by nature, evaluates himself, measures himself and even knows himself by transforming his energy and skill into the materials he collects from his environment and reflecting his character in the objects he creates (Erikson, 1986). In this context, the individual matches himself with the product he produces. This product does not necessarily have to be tangible. Intangible products and processes such as an idea, an invention, a personalized application can also create similar feelings.

The direct impact of automation on job characteristics can lead to employees' satisfaction or alienation from their work (Shepard, 1977). It has also been found that job alienation affects factors similar to and increasing the loss of job satisfaction in both individual and organizational contexts (Turgut & Kalafatoglu, 2016). In this context, reducing the alienation of the employee can be considered as a factor that will positively affect job satisfaction.

PCJ can also be seen as a factor that prevents the rupture in the relationship between the employees and their work, and in this study, the top and senior managers. The manager's ability to reflect his/her own character to his/her work and the fact that this is known by others may create an effect that strengthens the manager's relationship with his/her job by increasing his/her emotional and job satisfaction. Similarly, for managers who bring their personality to their work, their work and their reputation will support and improve each other. Therefore, managers may tend to feel more responsibility towards their work.

Performances of employees engaged in production lines based on automation and those who work for businesses in service and their executives can

be assessed almost invariably considering profitability and reproductivity due to current global dynamics, respectively. Attribution of the process to profitability in money can break off the bond between their personality as subjects and what they are producing in favor of targets of the business they work for. The concept of PCJ can be perceived only as business and trademark images related to work in terms of institutional expectations of the business world under current conditions. The concept of PCJ mentioned in our study is solely associated with the subject. It would not be wrong to suggest that personality contributions of the shoe maker who is expected to produce a pair of shoes all through its respects and in charge of its quality, individual shoe workers in production line who are supposed to simple automated tasks including shoe lacing, sole bonding, shoe upper process and checking stitches and an executive who has never worn it in his life to their jobs are of course different from each other.

The most disadvantageous group in personality contribution to job can be conceived as top managers who are technically in the most distant position possible to the job. What is essentially expected them to do is to increase their subordinates' performance enabling the jobs to be conducted under principles of the business. In this respect, the bond between the nature of the job and top management can be cited to have quite weakened. It is therefore possible for top managers to stay away from or deprive themselves of an intrinsic job satisfaction which could be gained only after they have contributed personality to their job.

4. Data Collection and Methodology

The data collection process started on March 20, 2023 and ended on March 30, 2023. After the participants were informed about the concepts of job satisfaction and adding personality to work, they were asked four open-ended questions prepared under the supervision of a panel of expert psychiatrists and psychologists:

- How would you describe being satisfied with your job? In the light of these explanations, do you think you are satisfied with your job?
- Could you list the 3 elements that make you satisfied with your job according to their importance? If you think that you are not satisfied enough with your job, could you list the 3 elements that will make you more satisfied according to their importance?
- Do you think that you can contri personality to your job in the context of the definition of "adding personality to work"?
- Would adding personality to your job be a satisfying factor for you? How would you rank the effect of this on your job satisfaction?

Interviews with the participants were conducted and recorded by video conference method. The data obtained from the interviews lasting 25-30 minutes were transferred to Microsoft Word application.

57 senior and top managers were requested to be interviewed about the study. Of these, 30 volunteered to participate in the study at the requested intensity. In-depth interviews were conducted with the participants for 25-30 minutes. The ages, sectors of employment, managerial experience and genders of the interviewed participants are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Participants

	Age	Managerial Experience (years)	Industry	Gender
P1	49	19	Manufacturing	F
P2	36	7	Manufacturing	M
P3	38	15	Service	M
P4	45	15	Manufacturing	M
P5	39	9	Manufacturing	M
P6	43	10	Manufacturing	M
P7	41	10	Manufacturing	M
P8	43	3	Service	M
P9	51	21	Manufacturing	M
P10	53	30	Service	M
P11	40	10	Manufacturing (Owner)	M
P12	47	20	Manufacturing (Owner)	M
P13	41	9	Service (Owner)	M
P14	49	20	Service	M
P15	42	10	Manufacturing	M
P16	52	15	Manufacturing	M
P17	48	20	Service	F
P18	44	10	Manufacturing	F
P19	52	20	Manufacturing	M
P20	46	19	Manufacturing	M
P21	57	33	Service	M
P22	39	15	Manufacturing	M
P23	41	12	Service	M
P24	42	13	Manufacturing	F
P25	41	20	Service (Owner)	M
P26	37	10	Manufacturing	M
P27	44	11	Manufacturing	M
P28	43	14	Manufacturing	F
P29	54	22	Manufacturing	M
P30	43	16	Service Owner)	F

In order to ensure that the answers to the questions included the sincere views of the participants, the participants were selected from those with whom the researcher had a certain closeness. Thus, it was aimed to increase the participants'

willingness to participate and to allocate more time to answer the research questions. In order to ensure diversity, care was taken to select managers operating in the manufacturing and service sectors.

The participants were first given the following information about the concept of PCJ:

- PCJ is when your work is directly associated with your name. In this case, you are directly responsible for the entire production process of a product produced in the company you work for. The end consumer or purchaser is aware of this situation and purchases/uses this product/process for this reason.
- An example of this is shoemakers. Old shoemakers used to carry out the entire production process of shoes. Therefore, the shoes sold were directly identified with the name of the shoemaker. The quality of the product and the reputation of the shoemaker were linked.
- In today's production systems and business world, it is not possible for a manager to take responsibility for the entire production process. In fact, managers devote a large part of their time to the management of the people who put these into practice rather than the products produced or the processes used in the organizations they work for.
- However, sometimes managers can gain experiences close to this situation by using a new product idea, a new production process understanding, a new management approach that is unique to them. Especially since senior and top managers are the stakeholders who are furthest away from the technical side of the business, the experience of such a situation can also be considered within the scope of PCJ.

After these information, open-ended questions were asked to the participants in a conversation and their answers were requested. Various examples and metaphors were used to make the questions clearer and more understandable for the participants.

The answers given by the participants were recorded through the video conferencing application where the interview was conducted. These interviews were then analyzed in detail, notes were taken and summarized. Member checking method was used to ensure the credibility of the findings. In the secondary interviews with the participants, the findings from the previous interview were read to the participants and they were asked to provide feedback. If there was new information that they wanted to change or add, these were added to the existing findings.

We first asked them what job satisfaction meant to themselves and if they were satisfied with their job or not. They were then requested to indicate the first

three (3) satisfactory factors to satisfy them in order of importance assuming that they were content with what they were doing at their current job.

It was later asked if they thought they were not pleased enough with those earlier jobs and similarly wanted to say other three factors to satisfy them in order of importance. Accordingly, they were informed on the concept of “Personality Contribution to Job (PCJ)” and thus requested to make an assessment of personal contribution to their job. Finally asked if they assumed they could contribute personality to their jobs, they were wanted to rank it in what order of the factors to satisfy them most. However, they were wanted to rank the factor of the job satisfaction in order of importance based on the fact that they could contribute personality to their jobs.

The answers to the questions will be interpretatively assessed to eventually predict the influence of executives ’contribution of personality on job satisfaction.

5. Findings

Table.2 shows the coded and organized data on the factors that the participants stated to provide job satisfaction and the order in which they ranked PCJ among these factors.

Table 2. Participants' Job Satisfaction Factors

	Three Most Important Job Satisfaction Sources			PCJ's Place In The Rankings
	1	2	3	
P1	Trust	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Love One's job	2
P2	Trust	Support	Wages and Fringe Benefits	3
P3	Being Planned	Merit	Wages and Fringe Benefits	3
P4	Sucess	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Team Cohession	3
P5	Support	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Being Planned	1
P6	Being Planned	Organizational Values	Wages and Fringe Benefits	-
P7	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Support	Sucess	-
P8	Love One's job	Nature of Work	Wages and Fringe Benefits	-
P9	Being Planned	Team Cohession	Sucess	1
P10	Love One's job	Providing Employment	Wages and Fringe Benefits	2
P11	Customer Satisfaction	Love One's job	Wages and Fringe Benefits	-

P12	Love One's job	Nature of Work	Change	2
P13	Reputation	Love One's job	Providing Employment	-
P14	Love One's job	Being Planned	Team Cohession	1
P15	Love One's job	Personal Development	Wages and Fringe Benefits	-
P16	Sucess	Support	Love One's job	-
P17	Love One's job	Support	Nature of Work	3
P18	Work Family Balance	Love One's job	Being Planned	-
P19	Love One's job	Sucess	Wages and Fringe Benefits	1
P20	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Customer Satisfaction	Support	2
P21	Sucess	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Team Cohession	2
P22	Team Cohession	Organizational Values	Wages and Fringe Benefits	2
P23	Nature of Work	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Merit	1
P24	Trust	Nature of Work	Support	-
P25	Team Cohession	Love One's job	Customer Satisfaction	1
P26	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Sucess	Organizational Values	-
P27	Nature of Work	Love One's job	Wages and Fringe Benefits	-
P28	Being Planned	Love One's job	Support	2
P29	Merit	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Personal Development	3
P30	Nature of Work	Wages and Fringe Benefits	Work – Family Balance	3

Four of the managers who participated in the interviews (P13, P14, P18 and P21) stated that they had an experience that fits the definition of "adding personality to their work". They expressed their views on the subject as follows:

P13: "I founded the company in a difficult economic period. We broke many grounds in Turkey. We worked with very big companies, which was satisfying for me at first. But then I realized that I was too attached to the business and could no longer spare time for myself. Even in situations that required the closure of the company financially, I ensured that the business continued by finding additional resources."

P14: "I am currently working as a general manager in one of the largest and oldest branches of one of the oldest institutions in Turkey. I was previously a regional manager. During this period, I produced and applied my own unique methods, and these methods were always referred to with my name both in my organization and in other institutions in the same sector. I wouldn't trade the satisfaction of this for anything. Even if I have to take a step back, I may want to return to the position of regional director just to experience this satisfaction."

P18: "I am the regional manager of one of the largest businesses in the US. This operation started with me. The reason why they wanted me for this operation is that the methods I developed for myself in the companies I worked in before brought high success and the customers preferred that company only because of my presence. At first, this situation was very satisfying for me. However, now financial conditions have become more important for me. I no longer get the same satisfaction from this situation as before."

P21: "Thanks to my experience in the sector, I have been a general manager and founding partner in many companies. Many applications are named after me. I realized more in this interview that this creates an important sense of satisfaction for me. I guess I didn't pay much attention to this in my daily concerns."

Others stated that they had not had such an experience. The managers were asked about their age and the duration of their managerial experience. In this context, there is no evidence that the age of the manager is directly related to the effect of adding personality to work behavior on satisfaction.

The majority of the managers with more than ten years of managerial experience (P1, P3, P4, P9, P10, P12, P14, P17, P19, P20, P21, P22, P23, P25, P28, P29, P30) stated that if they gained "PCJ" experience, the job satisfaction that this experience would create would be among the top three factors that cause job satisfaction for them.

At the same time, these managers also tend to rank job personalization higher than salary and benefits. Similarly, it is seen that the common emotion that creates job satisfaction among the managers who put adding personality to work in the top three ranks of satisfying factors is that they love the organization and sector they work in.

The majority of the managers with 10 years of managerial experience or less (P6, P7, P8, P11, P13, P15, P18, P26) stated that they did not consider "PCJ" experience as a source of satisfaction. More than half of these managers (P6, P7, P8, P11, P15, and P18) also ranked the satisfaction created by wages and benefits in the top three. The other managers (P11, P13 and P18) who did not rank wages

and fringe benefits as a satisfaction factor stated the reason for not considering PCJ as a satisfaction factor as follows:

P11: "I am both the top manager and the chairman of the board of directors. The name of the company is my middle name, so all the intensity is on my back. Sometimes I wish I had an ordinary salaried job. I cannot spare time for myself."

P13: "I raised the company with my own hands. I kept it afloat by transferring money from the family business to my own company in times of crisis. But I get very tired. If I had been an ordinary manager in the family business, maybe I would have been more comfortable and healthier."

P18: "I could have cared about this situation before I got married and had children, but now I prefer to spend more time for myself and my family."

Among the participants with more than 10 years of managerial experience, P16, P24 and P27 did not consider PCJ as an element of satisfaction. P16 explained this situation as follows:

"I am a pragmatist person. I am already satisfied enough with my work and the material/spiritual gains I get. Therefore, adding my work personality does not constitute an additional source of motivation for me."

P24 also made a similar statement:

"I do my job. I don't think I will be interested in what the job is after my material and moral expectations are met."

P27 mentioned a different reason:

"Communicating with people, developing them, empowering them, contributing to their betterment is a sufficient source of satisfaction for me. I don't think it is very important that my name is mentioned."

It is seen that managers operating in the service sector (P13, P14 and P21) are more likely to encounter situations that add personality to the job or create satisfaction close to it. In the manufacturing sector, on the other hand, no manager stated that he/she encountered situations that added personality to the job.

On the other hand, three of the managers who are both managers and business owners or partners (P11, P13, P30) do not consider the feeling of adding personality to work as an element of satisfaction or do not place it among the top three emotions that provide satisfaction for them. In a similar situation, two managers (P12 and P25) stated that they would be satisfied with PCJ. These two managers also mentioned "love one's job" as a source of satisfaction:

P12: Even though the company belongs to me, the name of the company is always in the foreground. I love what he does, I love taking care of the soil, it's a bit of a design job. I like to add something of myself here. Of course, I would feel even more satisfied if they were associated with my name."

P25: My job is education. I enjoy working with young people very much. Although the business I am a partner of is more prominent, I think it would be more satisfying if the students came here under my name.

The two of those managers (P14 and P18) without business ownership or partnership suggested that they used to feel content with PCJ as they were the regional executives at their businesses. One of them (P14) maintained that such a position quite pleased him adding that he could rank it in the first one of the three satisfactory factors and that he might even sacrifice his presently acquired employee personal rights returning to the position of the personality contribution at job that time just for the sake of its related job satisfaction though he was promoted to a higher status. The second executive (P18) stated that the present situation did not create satisfaction feeling then but could have created a seriously significant feeling of satisfaction if he had been asked early periods of his executives status. The first executive was employed by one of the established institutions for years and the second one has been working as a top manager for the recent operations in Turkey of a well-known international enterprise for over five years.

However, the one (P13) in charge of both management and ownership or partnership revealed that such a feeling failed to create satisfaction but tended to cost him adversities in business life instead. This executive adding personality to his work thus cited to complain about his overfocusing on tasks and failure to take time for himself. Although this feeling in addition caused him to excessively devote himself to job and then the financial position even forced the business to bring to the edge of closedown, he confessed having had to find a solution to the problem and reset things right by creating fresh capital through income from a family firm in which he was also included as the partner.

6. Conclusion and Discussion

Following automation, we see that rapidly developing production methods are rapidly leaving people out of the system. With the development of robotization and artificial intelligence, it seems inevitable that not only jobs that require muscle power but also jobs that require brain power will be automated. Although this situation does not seem like it will come to us in a very short time, the practices in this process are gradually pushing people to be only a part of the system as in the classical period. This situation leads to the alienation from work and loss of job satisfaction experienced by blue-collar workers working in production lines, which is now starting to be seen in managers as well. In some cases, existing production and management systems can assume a decision-making and organizing role. Thus, even some of the tasks of senior and top managers who make strategic decisions of organizations can be fulfilled by automation.

It would not be wrong to say that this situation inevitably causes a loss of job satisfaction in managers. The decline in job satisfaction also negatively affects the performance of managers, sometimes directly and sometimes indirectly. In order to prevent the loss of job satisfaction and to ensure that managers can regain their motivation, it is not easy to say that they have the same effect as before, although today, strengthening wages and fringe benefits still plays a more important

role. For this reason, various practices are used by organizations to make managers feel better in the organization they work for.

Our study was conducted with the idea that PCJ can be one of these practices. The findings show that PCJ can be a factor that increases job satisfaction in senior and top managers. However, the evidence has been found to indicate that this situation widely exist in the executives professionally engaged in manufacturing sector where titles of institutions are inevitably chosen to be emphasized first, which could stem from executives or top managers being almost completely alienated from the nature of the business. Now that output produced by businesses in manufacturing sector are the physical items, they can further appeal to physical senses of executives. It is therefore possible to say that impacts of personality contribution on job satisfaction are relatively strong in manufacturing industry.

Such a feeling can be suggested to create less satisfaction perception among executives involved in service industry, which is of course to be attributable to the nature of the job. However high the status of executives can be in service industry, those involved in the sector can be seen to be so influenced by PCJ as those engaged in manufacturing processes both because they can not stay away from work and because what has been produced is not a physical item but just a service instead.

Those working both as executives and owners or partners can be suggested to constitute the group to create the least job satisfaction in terms of PCJ, which the interviewed executives currently tried to reveal “the title of the business is the same as or similar to my name and or surname anyway” adding that they experienced the feeling of PCJ or what ever feels similar to that feeling. This phenomenon can be assessed as the reason why PCJ created less influence than other characteristics to create job satisfaction in executives who work as executives and owners or partners.

In conclusion, the feeling of PCJ produces more job satisfaction in those with longer tenure or managerial experience and further emphasis on the nature and surrounding of work. However, job satisfaction created by PCJ can be said to remain less than usual in those with comparatively shorter tenure and lower managerial experience. The feeling of PCJ can be suggested to fail to create or hardly create any job satisfaction in those in charge of both management and ownership or partnership in the business. The feeling of PCJ can be said to be the case not encountered in manufacturing sector whereas it can be seen more frequently in service industry. Those with feeling of PCJ or similar feelings such as love of their jobs and longer tennure or managerial experience can be claimed to have the highest job satisfaction therefrom. On the other hand, those in the positions of ownership and managing or partnership can be described as individuals who have the least job satisfaction from the feeling of PCJ.

Studies to be made together with more and a variety of businesses are likely to shed light on more different and richer findings. We can therefore conclude that research could emerge which would be performed within a wide range of means

to establish and analyze the influence of the feeling of PCJ on executives and staff members in terms of job satisfaction.

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